

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF RHENIUM(IV) COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
		Re	N	OI		
$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{Pa})_4$	Dark brown	44.12 (48.89)	18.15 (18.30)	20.28 (20.27)	828.4 (818.4)	0.67
$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{MePa})_4$	Light brown	42.09 (41.17)	12.42 (12.38)	19.14 (19.01)	880.6 (874.4)	0.78
$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{DmPa})_4$	Brown	38.72 (38.77)	11.85 (11.66)	18.01 (17.90)	941.2 (930.4)	0.71
$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{TmPa})_4$	Brown	36.51 (36.84)	11.19 (11.02)	16.87 (16.92)	980.1 (986.4)	0.69
$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{TeTmPa})_4$	Deep brown	34.28 (34.72)	10.60 (10.44)	16.17 (16.04)	1055 (1042.4)	0.75

perrhenate with potassium iodide in concentrated hydrochloric acid medium⁸.

Preparation of complexes: An aqueous solution of potassium hexachlororhenate (0.005 mol) was mixed with an aqueous ethanolic solution of the Me-pyrazoles (0.040 mol) and warmed. The resulting deep chocolate coloured solution on concentration at room temperature gave brown-dark brown crystals, which were washed with cold methanol and petroleum ether and dried over fused calcium chloride. The complexes were further recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether. The compounds were soluble in all common organic solvents like methanol and acetone, but insoluble in water and petroleum ether. Elemental analyses data are presented in Table 1.

Room temperature (298 K) magnetic moment (μ_{eff}), molar conductance (Λ_M) in methanol, electronic spectra (methanol) and ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded and their molecular weights in chloroform were determined by ebullioscopic method.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis data (Table 1) correspond to the general formula ReOCl_2L_2 for the complexes. Molecular weight data indicate the complexes to be dimeric. Low molar conductance ($10-15 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) values of the complexes show their non-electrolytic nature. The electronic spectra of the complexes gave two bands at 27 400 and 16 500 cm^{-1} corresponding to the transitions ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ respectively suggesting rhenium(IV) in a typical octahedral environment⁹. The ν_{NH} bands in the ir spectra of the complexes were somewhat diffused and the ring vibrations were lowered due to complex formation⁶. A strong band around 897-910 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{Re=O}}$ was observed in all the complexes⁵⁻⁸. Another strong band around 305-310 cm^{-1} was due to $\nu_{\text{Re-Cl}}$ ⁹. The μ_{eff} values of the complexes were unusually low (0.65-0.75 B.M.) for rhenium(IV) ion with three unpaired electrons⁴⁻⁶. The lowering may be due to chloride-bridged (A) or oxobridged (B) binuclear structure of these complexes.

The presence of $\nu_{\text{Re=O}}$ band in the ir spectra of the complexes suggests the chloride-bridged structure (A) more plausible for these complexes.

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Beryllium(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of Methyl 2-Phenylazo-3-oxobutanoate

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[N continuation of our studies on 2-arylozo-1,3-dicarbonyls and their metal complexes¹⁻⁴, we report the synthesis and characterisation of the Be^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of methyl 2-phenylazo-3-oxobutanoate (phenylazomethylacetate, HL).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. °C	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
			O	H	N	Metal
CuL ₂	175	Deep green	52.10 (52.68)	4.38 (4.89)	10.98 (11.16)	12.60 (12.67)
NiL ₂	240	Dull green	49.50 (49.98)	3.98 (4.12)	10.80 (10.50)	10.97 (11.07)
CoL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	220	Greenish yellow	53.00 (53.15)	4.10 (4.48)	11.20 (11.27)	11.80 (11.82)
BeL ₂	215	Yellow	58.40 (59.06)	4.80 (4.92)	12.15 (12.59)	1.98 (2.02)

Experimental

Phenylazomethylacetoacetate was prepared as reported⁸. Metal complexes were prepared as follows. To a solution of the ligand (5 mmol) in methanol (50 ml) was added an aqueous solution (15 ml) of the metal(II) acetate (2.5 mmol). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h, concentrated to about 25 ml and cooled in ice. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from hot ethanol.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis data (Table 1) correspond to 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry for all the complexes. The molar conductance of the complexes in methanol lies below $10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ indicating their non-electrolytic nature.

Reactions of aryldiazonium salts with 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds lead to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded 1,2,3-tricarbonyl-2-arylhydrazones rather than in any of the other alternative tautomeric forms¹⁻⁸. Electronic, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data indicate that phenyl azomethylacetoacetate exists as the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded arylhydrazone tautomer (1a). Thus, the ir spectrum of the compound revealed two strong bands at 1 725 and 1 625 cm^{-1} assignable to conjugated free ester carbonyl and to hydrogen bonded acetyl carbonyl, respectively, and a very broad band at 2 800–3 100 cm^{-1} due to the internally hydrogen bonded structure⁷. The uv spectrum (methanol) of the compound showed absorption at 300–360 nm (maximum at 345 nm) characteristic of the hydrazone form⁸. The ¹H nmr spectrum of the compound (in CDCl₃) showed a low-field one-proton signal at δ 14.50 for its chelated NH

proton^{8,9}. The methyl protons of acetyl and ester groups absorb at δ 2.50 (s) and 3.70 (s), respectively, and the phenyl protons at δ 7.50 (m). Integrated intensities of these signals are as expected.

Uv spectra (methanol) of the metal chelates bear close resemblance to that of the ligand. It is, therefore, evident that no structural alteration of the ligand occurs during complexation. Ir spectra of the metal chelates are compatible with the structure that would result, if the chelated hydrogen of the ligand is replaced by metal ion as in structure 1b. Thus, the position of the free ester carbonyl band of the ligand is only marginally altered in the spectra of the metal chelates. Instead of the free ligand band at 1 625 cm^{-1} , spectra of all the metal chelates exhibit another strong band at $\sim$ 1 550 cm^{-1} assignable to metal bonded acetyl carbonyl⁹. A weak band attributable to conjugated $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ appears at $\sim$ 1 615 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the metal chelates. In the spectrum of the ligand this band is presumably masked by the strong absorption of hydrogen bonded acetyl carbonyl. The broad band of the ligand at 2 800–3 100 cm^{-1} disappears in the spectra of the metal chelates and instead weak bands at $\sim$ 3 050 (aromatic CH) and $\sim$ 2 950 cm^{-1} (aliphatic C-H) appear in the spectra of the chelates. Cobalt(II) complex exhibits a broad band at 3 550 cm^{-1} , presumably due to its coordinated water.

Ir spectra of all the metal chelates showed a medium intensity band at 520–560 (M-N) and 400–440 cm^{-1} (M-O). Similar assignments have been made earlier in the case of metal chelates of arylazo-1,3-diketones^{9,10}. The low-field signal of the ligand at δ 14.50 due to hydrogen bonded NH is absent in the ¹H nmr spectra of the diamagnetic Be^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, indicating replacement of the NH proton during metal chelation. Thus, the evidences suggest that phenylazomethylacetoacetate acts as monobasic bidentate and bound to the metal ion through the hydrazino nitrogen and the acyl oxygen (1b).

The observed magnetic moment (1.92 B.M.) and a broad visible band with maximum at 14 810 cm^{-1} indicate square-planar geometry for the Cu^{II} chelate¹⁰. The diamagnetism of the Ni^{II} complex and a band at 22 220 cm^{-1} suggests its square-planar geometry¹⁰. The electronic spectrum of the Co^{II} complex is characterised by a broad ν_s

1a
1b
where M = Be^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}.

